

A Study on the Impact of Socio-Economic Factors and Perception of Tribals towards the Growth and Development of Tribal Businesses in the Nilgiris District

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Abstract : *This study investigates the impact of socio-economic factors and perception on the growth and development of tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district. The study aims to understand the demographics of the respondents, the types of tribal businesses, the marketing strategies adopted, and the level of satisfaction towards the availability and accessibility of resources. A quantitative research design was used to collect data from a sample of 112 tribal business owners in the Nilgiris district. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics to draw conclusions and make recommendations. The study found that the majority of respondents were in the age group of 26 to 45 years, had no formal education, and resided in pucca or semi-pucca houses. Animal husbandry, handicrafts, and agriculture/horticulture were the most common types of tribal businesses, and social media marketing was the most popular marketing strategy adopted by tribal businesses. The perception of marketing strategies adopted by tribal businesses was positive, with innovative and modern marketing strategies being considered the most effective. Additionally, the availability and accessibility of physical resources, technical assistance, and marketing assistance were found to be crucial for the success of tribal businesses. The study concluded that demographics did not play a significant role in the perception of marketing strategies adopted and the level of satisfaction towards the availability and accessibility of resources. Therefore, businesses should focus on adopting effective marketing strategies and improving their access to resources to increase their chances of success, regardless of their target audience's demographics.*

Keywords : Tribal Businesses, Socio-economic Factors, Perception, Nilgiris District, Growth and Development.

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1.0. Introduction

The Nilgiris district is home to several tribal communities, each with its unique culture, traditions, and economic activities. Tribal businesses in the district face several challenges in terms of accessing resources, marketing their products effectively, and expanding their businesses. These challenges are further compounded by the socio-economic factors that affect the growth and development of tribal businesses in the region. Therefore, it is essential to understand the impact of these factors and the perception of tribals towards the growth and development of tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district.

This study aims to investigate the impact of socio-economic factors and perception on the growth and development of tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district. The study will focus on understanding the demographics of the respondents, the types of tribal businesses, the marketing strategies adopted, and the level of satisfaction towards the availability and accessibility of resources. The study will also explore the association between demographics and perception of marketing strategies and level of satisfaction towards the availability and accessibility of resources for tribal businesses in the district.

The study will use a quantitative research design to collect data from a sample of tribal business owners in the Nilgiris district. The data will be collected through a structured questionnaire, which will be distributed to the respondents using convenience sampling. The questionnaire will include questions on demographics, types of businesses, marketing strategies, and resources. The data will be analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics to draw conclusions and make recommendations for tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district.

The findings of the study will provide valuable insights into the socio-economic factors and perception of tribals towards the growth and development of tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district. The study will help tribal business owners and entrepreneurs to understand the challenges and opportunities in the region and design their marketing strategies accordingly. The study will also inform policymakers and other stakeholders about the resources needed to promote the growth of tribal businesses in the region.

This study is essential for understanding the impact of socio-economic factors and perception on the growth and development of tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district. The study will provide valuable insights into the demographics of the respondents, types of tribal businesses, marketing strategies adopted, and level of satisfaction towards the availability and accessibility of resources.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the impact of demographic variables on the marketing strategies adopted and the level of satisfaction towards the availability and accessibility of resources for tribal businesses in the Nilgiris District.
2. To analyze the perception of marketing strategies adopted by tribal businesses and their impact on the growth and development of tribal businesses in the Nilgiris District.

2.0. Review of Literature

R.Rubini and Dr.K.Mangayarkarasi. (2021), The objective of this study was to examine the socio-economic status of Toda Tribal Women in Nilgiri District and to estimate their level of empowerment through education, employment, income, and ownership. The research methodology employed involved selecting 110 empowered women through convenient sampling from five settlements, namely Garden Mund, ManjakalMund, FurnelMund, TamizhagamMund, and Glen Morgan Mund. The data obtained from the women respondents were analyzed using basic statistical methods, such as frequency, cross-tabulation, chi-square, and t-test. The study found that education and employment are crucial factors affecting the social and economic empowerment of Toda tribal women. The government can help improve their status by providing support and grants for education and employment opportunities. The study concludes that increasing the literacy rate and providing opportunities for gainful employment for tribal women will be instrumental in bringing about a change in the status of tribal women in India and to handle the challenges successfully.

Selva Kumar D.S and Siva Kumar S. (2014), the objective of this study was to identify the current socio-economic conditions of tribal populations in the Nilgiris district and suggest possible solutions to improve their per capita income, GDP, social status, expenditure pattern, and lifestyle. The research methodology involved surveying a random sample of 100 households, with the data collected from reliable sources like Census of India, Times of India Newspaper, BPL survey 2002, etc. The study found that illiteracy is still prevalent among the SC and ST populations, poverty is more among the ST population, and the government spending on their welfare needs attention. The study suggests the need for a separate organization to address the requirements of the SC and ST populations for equalitarian growth in society. Unless progress is made, the progress in Human Development Index (HDI) cannot be achieved.

D.Kasturi. (2019), The objective of this study was to determine the factors that affect women empowerment among Kurumba tribes in Nilgiris, including socio-demographic and socio-economic factors. The research methodology involved an explanatory research design using quantitative analysis to establish the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Primary data were collected through a survey instrument prepared for the study, with 150 samples selected from a small village with a total population of 240 in Nilgiris District. The study found that the lack of access to knowledge and job opportunities were major drawbacks for tribal women, and suggested implementing skill development, entrepreneurial training, microfinance, and participation in SHG activities to improve their socio-economic status. The study concludes that efforts and support from government agencies and NGOs are crucial in increasing knowledge and awareness among tribal women, which directly improves their socio-economic levels and women empowerment.

M. Panneerselvam et al. (2020), The objective of this study was to assess the quality of life of Todas, a Scheduled tribe in Nilgiri district, and to identify the factors influencing their quality of life. The research methodology involved collecting data from 50 Todas households in Nanjanadu village, Udhagamandalam block, using parameters such as housing, water source, sanitation facilities, food and nutrition intake, health status, education, fuel and energy availability, assets, transportation, and per capita income. Chi-square analysis was used to analyze the data. The study found that 48% of Todas were involved in business and the average monthly income was Rs. 7521. Majority of Todas lived in joint families and in Kacha houses with their own toilet facilities. The study recommended increasing access to education facilities and income generation programs targeting women to improve the quality of life of Todas. The study concluded that quality of life is a crucial aspect of development, and that efforts must be made to improve the quality of life of all Scheduled tribes in India.

Arunmozhi M. S. (2016). This study examined the financial inclusion services provided by banks and their awareness among the tribal community in a selected sample of villages, in comparison to government policies. The research methodology included the collection of primary data through questionnaires from 639 respondents selected through purposive sampling. The findings revealed that 70% of respondents had a bank account, and 52.9% had awareness of the no-frill account scheme. However, more than half of the account holders did not exhibit saving behavior. The study suggested increasing awareness of the benefits of no-frill saving accounts, providing financial literacy centers in

every place, and increasing awareness among illiterate and poor people. The study concluded that while the financial inclusion scheme had a strong social mission, it had not been fully translated into satisfactory action on the ground, and more efforts were needed to improve the awareness and standard of living of the tribal community.

3.0. Research Methodology

The research methodology for this study involved the collection of primary data through a survey conducted among 112 respondents in the Nilgiris district. The sampling technique used for this study was convenience sampling, where respondents were selected based on their availability and willingness to participate in the survey. The survey questionnaire was designed to collect information on the demographic variables, marketing strategies adopted by tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district, the perception of marketing strategies adopted by tribal businesses, and the level of satisfaction towards the availability and accessibility of resources for the tribal businesses. The data collected was analyzed using statistical tools such as frequency analysis, descriptive statistics, Correlation Analysis and Anova Analysis tests to draw conclusions and make recommendations.

4.0 Analysis and Interpretation

Table No.1: Table displaying the Demographic details of respondents

Demographic factors	Variables	No. of Respondents	Percent
Age Group	Upto 25 years	13	11.6
	26 to 35 years	40	35.7
	35 to 45 years	40	35.7
	Above 45 years	19	17.0
Gender	Male	61	54.5
	Female	51	45.5
Monthly income	Upto Rs.15000	49	43.8
	Rs.15001 to Rs.30000	43	38.4
	Rs.30001 to Rs.45000	14	12.5
	Above Rs.45000	6	5.4
Education	No formal education	73	65.2
	Completed primary education	27	24.1
	Completed high school education	12	10.7

(Contd...)

House Type	Pucca house (concrete or brick walls with a concrete roof)	48	42.9
	Semi-pucca house (concrete or brick walls with a thatched or tin roof)	49	43.8
	Kutcha house (mud walls with a thatched roof)	15	13.4
Tribal Community	Todas	32	28.6
	Kurumbas	18	16.1
	Irulas	15	13.4
	Paniyas	17	15.2
	Kotas	15	13.4
	Badagas	15	13.4
Location	Gudalur	15	13.4
	Kotagiri	39	34.8
	Coonoor	23	20.5
	Ooty	23	20.5
	Kundah	12	10.7

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: The table no. 1 displays the demographic details of the respondents and provides insights into their characteristics and behavior. The age group distribution of the respondents indicates that the majority (71.4%) fall under the age group of 26 to 45 years, while only a small percentage (17%) are above 45 years, and the youngest age group, up to 25 years, had the least number of respondents (11.6%). The gender distribution of the respondents is almost equal, with 54.5% being male and 45.5% being female. In terms of monthly income, more than 80% of the respondents have a monthly income of up to Rs. 30,000, with the majority (43.8%) earning up to Rs. 15,000, and only a small percentage (5.4%) having an income above Rs. 45,000. The majority of the respondents (65.2%) have no formal education, while 24.1% have completed primary education, and only 10.7% have completed high school education. The majority of respondents (86.7%) have pucca or semi-pucca houses, while only a small percentage (13.4%) have kutcha houses. Todas (28.6%) and Kurumbas (16.1%) are the two largest tribal communities represented in the survey. Finally, the largest number of respondents come from Kotagiri (34.8%), followed by Coonoor and Ooty (both 20.5%), while the smallest number of respondents come from Gudalur (13.4%). Overall, this data provides valuable insights into the demographic profile of the respondents, which can be useful in understanding their characteristics and behavior.

Table No.2 : Types of Tribal Business

Types of Tribal Business	No. of Respondents	Percent
Agriculture and Horticulture	22	19.6
Handicrafts	27	24.1
Animal Husbandry	35	31.2
Forest Products	22	19.6
Tourism	6	5.4
Total	112	100.0

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: The table no. 2 suggests that the most common type of tribal business in the Nilgiris district is animal husbandry, followed by handicrafts and agriculture/horticulture. Forest products and tourism are less popular.

Table No.3: Marketing strategies adopted by tribal businesses in the Nilgiris District

Marketing strategies adopted by tribal businesses in the Nilgiris District	No. of Respondents	Percent
Cultural and traditional marketing	50	20.8
Social media marketing	60	25.0
Collaborative marketing	40	16.7
Event marketing	25	10.4
Eco-tourism marketing	23	9.6
Eco-tourism marketing	42	17.5
Total	240	100.0

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: The table no.3 provides a breakdown of the marketing strategies used by tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district, with social media marketing being the most popular method, followed by cultural and traditional marketing, collaborative marketing, and eco-tourism marketing. Event marketing and eco-tourism marketing had the lowest percentages.

Table No.4 : Perception of marketing strategies adopted by Tribal businesses in Nilgiris District

Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation
Tribal business strategies effectively promote products.	2.26	1.05
Tribal business strategies reflect cultural heritage.	2.35	1.19
Tribal business strategies meet target market preferences.	2.47	1.08
Tribal business strategies are sustainable and eco-friendly.	2.14	1.04
Tribal business strategies are affordable and feasible.	2.37	0.82
Tribal business strategies adapt to changing markets.	2.24	0.93
Tribal business strategies are innovative and modern.	2.54	1.06
Tribal business strategies prioritize customer satisfaction.	2.43	1.06
Tribal business strategies are accessible to customers.	2.28	1.25
Tribal business strategies increase product visibility and reach.	2.23	1.00

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: From the above table no.4, the descriptive statistics for the Perception of marketing strategies adopted by Tribal businesses in Nilgiris District are ranked from 'Tribal business strategies are innovative and modern.' stood at first with the highest mean score 2.54, followed by 'Tribal business strategies meet target market preferences.' stood at second with the mean score 2.47, 'Tribal business strategies prioritize customer satisfaction.' stood at third with the mean score 2.43, 'Tribal business strategies are affordable and feasible.' stood at fourth with the mean score 2.37, 'Tribal business strategies reflect cultural heritage.' stood at fifth with the mean score 2.35, 'Tribal business strategies are accessible to customers.' stood at sixth with the mean score 2.28, 'Tribal business strategies effectively promote products.' stood at seventh with the mean score 2.26, 'Tribal business strategies adapt to changing markets.' stood at eighth with the mean score 2.24, 'Tribal business strategies increase product visibility and reach.' stood at ninth with the mean score 2.23, and finally 'Tribal business strategies are sustainable and eco-friendly.' stood at tenth with the mean score 2.14.

Table No.5 : Level of satisfaction towards the Availability and Accessibility of resources for the Tribal businesses in Nilgiris District

Availability and Accessibility of resources	Mean	Std. Deviation
Financial resources (Ex:credit, microfinance, and other financial resource)	2.50	0.94
Physical resources (Ex: land, water, electricity, and other infrastructure required)	2.61	0.99
Technical assistance (Ex: product design, quality control, and packaging)	2.61	1.23
Marketing assistance (Ex: branding, advertising, and market research)	2.59	1.28
Government policies and support (Ex: subsidies, tax incentives, and training programs)	2.37	1.10
Economic conditions (Ex: inflation and exchange rates)	2.48	1.00

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: From the above table no.5, the descriptive statistics for the Level of satisfaction towards the Availability and Accessibility of resources for the Tribal businesses in Nilgiris District are ranked from ‘Physical resources (Ex: land, water, electricity, and other infrastructure required)’ stood at first with the highest mean score 2.61, followed by ‘Technical assistance (Ex: product design, quality control, and packaging)’ stood at first with the mean score 2.61, ‘Marketing assistance (Ex: branding, advertising, and market research)’ stood at second with the mean score 2.59, ‘Financial resources (Ex:credit, microfinance, and other financial resource)’ stood at third with the mean score 2.50, ‘Economic conditions (Ex: inflation and exchange rates)’ stood at fourth with the mean score 2.48, and finally ‘Government policies and support (Ex: subsidies, tax incentives, and training programs)’ stood at fifth with the mean score 2.37.

Table No.6 : Hypothesis Testing

Null Hypothesis (H₀) : There is no significant correlation between marketing strategies adopted and satisfaction with the availability of resources for tribal businesses in Nilgiris.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁) : There is a significant correlation between marketing strategies adopted and satisfaction with the availability of resources for tribal businesses in Nilgiris.

Correlations			
		Perception of marketing strategies adopted by Tribal businesses in Nilgiris District	Level of satisfaction towards the Availability and Accessibility of resources for the Tribal businesses in Nilgiris District
Perception of marketing strategies adopted by Tribal businesses in Nilgiris District	Pearson Correlation	1	.635**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	112	112
Level of satisfaction towards the Availability and Accessibility of resources for the Tribal businesses in Nilgiris District	Pearson Correlation	.635**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	112	112
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Inference : The table No.6 shows that the Pearson correlation coefficient between these two variables is 0.635, which indicates a moderately strong positive correlation. However, the p-value (sig. 2-tailed) is 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.01. This means that the null hypothesis (H₀) of no significant correlation is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) of a significant correlation is accepted. Therefore, the data suggests that there is a significant correlation between the perception of marketing strategies adopted and the level of satisfaction towards the availability and accessibility of resources for tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district. This indicates that businesses that adopt effective marketing strategies are more likely to be satisfied with the availability and accessibility of resources.

Table No.7

Null Hypothesis (H₀) : There is no significant association between the demographic variables and Perception of marketing strategies adopted by Tribal businesses in Nilgiris District.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁) : There is a significant association between the demographic variables and Perception of marketing strategies adopted by Tribal businesses in Nilgiris District

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Age Group	Between Groups	16.104	17	.947	1.185	.292
	Within Groups	75.173	94	.800		
	Total	91.277	111			
Monthly income	Between Groups	11.832	17	.696	.929	.543
	Within Groups	70.444	94	.749		
	Total	82.277	111			
Education	Between Groups	9.766	17	.574	1.285	.219
	Within Groups	42.011	94	.447		
	Total	51.777	111			
House Type	Between Groups	9.505	17	.559	1.201	.279
	Within Groups	43.772	94	.466		
	Total	53.277	111			
Tribal Community	Between Groups	44.604	17	2.624	.789	.701
	Within Groups	312.503	94	3.325		
	Total	357.107	111			
Location	Between Groups	19.013	17	1.118	.717	.779
	Within Groups	146.665	94	1.560		
	Total	165.679	111			
Types of Tribal Business	Between Groups	26.351	17	1.550	1.190	.288
	Within Groups	122.426	94	1.302		
	Total	148.777	111			

Inference: The table no.7 shows that the p-values (sig.) for all the demographic variables are greater than the significance level of 0.05, indicating that there is no significant association between the demographic variables and the perception of marketing strategies adopted. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H₀) of no

significant association is accepted, and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) of a significant association is rejected. The data suggests that the demographic variables do not play a significant role in determining the perception of marketing strategies adopted by tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district.

Table No.8

Null Hypothesis (H_0) : There is no significant association between the demographic variables and Level of satisfaction towards the Availability and Accessibility of resources for the Tribal businesses in Nilgiris District.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1) : There is a significant association between the demographic variables and Level of satisfaction towards the Availability and Accessibility of resources for the Tribal businesses in Nilgiris District.

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Age Group	Between Groups	16.843	25	.674	.778	.758
	Within Groups	74.434	86	.866		
	Total	91.277	111			
Monthly income	Between Groups	17.892	25	.716	.956	.532
	Within Groups	64.385	86	.749		
	Total	82.277	111			
Education	Between Groups	6.814	25	.273	.521	.967
	Within Groups	44.963	86	.523		
	Total	51.777	111			
House Type	Between Groups	9.314	25	.373	.729	.814
	Within Groups	43.963	86	.511		
	Total	53.277	111			
Tribal Community	Between Groups	41.147	25	1.646	.448	.987
	Within Groups	315.960	86	3.674		
	Total	357.107	111			
Location	Between Groups	57.736	25	2.309	1.840	.020
	Within Groups	107.942	86	1.255		
	Total	165.679	111			
Types of Tribal Business	Between Groups	34.562	25	1.382	1.041	.427
	Within Groups	114.215	86	1.328		
	Total	148.777	111			

Source : Field Study.

Inference : The table no.8 shows that the p-values (sig.) for age group, monthly income, education, and house type are greater than the significance level of 0.05, indicating that there is no significant association between these variables and the level of satisfaction towards resource availability and accessibility. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H₀) of no significant association is accepted, and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) of a significant association is rejected for these variables. However, for the location variable, the p-value is 0.020, which is less than the significance level of 0.05. This suggests that there is a significant association between location and the level of satisfaction towards resource availability and accessibility. The data suggests that the location of tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district may have a significant impact on their level of satisfaction towards the availability and accessibility of resources. Other demographic variables do not appear to have a significant association.

5.0. Discussion on Findings :

Majority of the respondents were in the age group of 26 to 45 years (71.4%). Male respondents were slightly higher than female respondents (54.5% vs. 45.5%). Majority of the respondents had no formal education (65.2%). Semi-pucca houses were the most common type of housing (43.8%). The largest tribal communities represented were Todas (28.6%) and Kurumbas (16.1%). Kotagiri had the highest number of respondents (34.8%).

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the majority of respondents engaged in Animal Husbandry (31.2%), followed by Handicrafts (24.1%) and Agriculture and Horticulture (19.6%). The most commonly adopted marketing strategy by tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district was social media marketing (25%), followed by cultural and traditional marketing (20.8%). The perception of marketing strategies adopted by tribal businesses was generally positive, with the highest mean score for “tribal business strategies are innovative and modern” (2.54), while the lowest mean score was for “tribal business strategies are sustainable and eco-friendly” (2.14).

The study also found a significant positive correlation between the perception of marketing strategies adopted by tribal businesses and the level of satisfaction towards the availability and accessibility of resources. However, there was no significant association between demographic variables and either the perception of marketing strategies or the level of satisfaction towards the availability and accessibility of resources.

6.0 Conclusions:

The primary data analysis of a survey conducted in the Nilgiris district reveals key recommendations and conclusions that can help businesses targeting the local tribal population. The majority of the respondents are between 26 to 45 years old, have a monthly income of up to Rs.30,000, and reside in pucca or semi-pucca houses. Animal husbandry is the most common type of tribal business, followed by handicrafts and agriculture/horticulture. Social media marketing is the most popular marketing strategy adopted by tribal businesses. Innovative and modern marketing strategies are effective in promoting products, meeting target market preferences, and prioritizing customer satisfaction, according to tribal businesses. Moreover, the availability and accessibility of resources play a crucial role in the success of tribal businesses, especially physical resources, technical assistance, and marketing assistance.

There is no significant association between demographics and the perception of marketing strategies adopted and the level of satisfaction towards the availability and accessibility of resources. Therefore, businesses should focus on adopting effective marketing strategies and improving their access to resources to increase their chances of success, regardless of their target audience's demographics. The government and other stakeholders should focus on providing resources to promote the growth of tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district. To maximize their chances of success, businesses should adopt innovative marketing strategies and improve their access to physical resources, technical assistance, and marketing assistance. Overall, this analysis provides valuable insights into the demographic profile of the respondents, types of tribal businesses, marketing strategies, and availability and accessibility of resources for tribal businesses in the Nilgiris district.

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